

STUDIES IN GLASS SYSTEMS. MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY OF POLAR CRYSTALS DISSOLVED IN BORAX GLASS

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The magnetic susceptibility of solid systems consisting of LiCl, NaCl and KCl dissolved in borax glass at different concentrations has been measured and the value for the dissolved alkali halide has been calculated from the additivity formula. These values show departure from their normal values as would be expected from the Fajans theory of deformation applied to solid solutions. But the variation is in an opposite sense as would be expected from theoretical considerations.

Majumdar and co-workers (Wulff and Majumdar, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, 31, 319; Majumdar and Sarma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 461) have studied polar crystals like alkali halides dissolved in B_2O_3 glass. Using the mole-refraction method, they have found that the Fajans rule of deformation holds good *qualitatively* in solid solutions of alkali halides dissolved in glass systems. In the present paper, the magnetic susceptibility of the three salts, LiCl, NaCl and KCl, dissolved in fused borax glass at different concentrations, have been determined by Guoy's method.

The relation between the magnetic properties of a substance and its internal structure has of late received very considerable attention. The salts studied in this paper are all diamagnetic having ions with inert gas configurations. It is interesting to note whether the magnetic susceptibility of these salts vary with concentration in the glass and, if so, at what rate.

It is well known that Pascal in his classical work, working mostly with nonpolar substances laid down the additivity formula for the diamagnetic susceptibility of molecules. If χ_m be the molecular susceptibility of a diamagnetic molecule, then according to Pascal,

$$\chi_m = A \sum \chi_A + \lambda, \text{ where } A \sum \chi_A$$

is the sum of the atomic susceptibilities and λ is the constitutive constant depending on the nature of the linkage. Whether Pascals' law holds good for all compounds, including polar compounds in the solid state and in state of solution, has formed the subject matter of numerous investigations in recent years.

Although very extended investigations have been made concerning magnetic properties of alloy systems, solutions of salts and to a limited extent the solid salts themselves, little work seems to have been done with binary systems of salts. The former has been studied among others by Honda and Sone (*Sci. Rep., Tokoku Imp. Univ.*, 1913, 2, 1; 1925, 14, 479), Garrison (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 622), Spencer and John (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, 116, A, 61) and with binary systems of salts by Bhatnagar and Kapur (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 347). They examined the magnetic properties of solid solutions of $KMnO_4$ - $KClO_4$, KCl - $NaCl$, KBr - KCl and KBr - $NaBr$ systems and found that in the system $KMnO_4$ - $KClO_4$ the susceptibility-concentration curve is a straight line, while in the remaining systems curved graphs are obtained. In other words the susceptibility-concentration curves may either follow a linear course or the curve may pass through a

maximum. These workers have tried to correlate the heat of formation of the systems with their magnetic susceptibility. When the heat of formation is zero, the susceptibility-concentration curve is a straight line; in other cases the curve passes through a maximum. This point is of some importance in the present investigation. As will be seen later, the susceptibility-concentration curves become linear when the salts in different proportions are simply intimately mixed with borax, while a different type of curve is obtained when the same system is previously melted.

EXPERIMENTAL

The salts from which the samples were prepared were Merck's *pro Analyse* variety excepting LiCl which was specially purified. The latter, which was extremely hygroscopic, was heated in a platinum basin and the dried mass digested with a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether, in which only LiCl dissolved. The solution was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. Before preparing a sample for measurement, the salt was kept at a high temperature for several hours. The other salts were carefully dehydrated for a pretty long time.

Borax was powdered and kept in thin layers in an air oven for several hours until a little portion of it digested with absolute alcohol did not give coloration with anhydrous copper sulphate. The anhydrous borax was then kept in a vacuum desiccator for several days.

Different samples were prepared by taking the dehydrated borax and alkali halide in varying proportions in a platinum crucible and heating to temperature of 900-1000° for eight to ten hours until a thoroughly homogeneous melt was obtained. A portion of the ingredients sublimed off before melting but afterwards a melt of constant composition was obtained. The crucible was then chilled by placing it on a cooled surface when the solidified mass cracked. The solid was then detached, transferred to a sample tube and preserved in a vacuum desiccator until use. The samples presented a thoroughly transparent appearance even after several weeks. Each sample was examined under crossed Nicols in a polarising microscope; it remained dark in all positions indicating that although borax crystals were anisotropic, its glass was isotropic. Before each experiment, the pieces were powdered in an agate mortar.

Analysis of the Samples.—The chlorine content of the samples was determined volumetrically in nitric acid solution by back titration method. A definite weight of the glass was dissolved in hot water and excess of nitric acid added. A check was made in the case of the NaCl—Na₂B₄O₇ systems by estimating the total amount of sodium as Na₂SO₄ by repeatedly heating with HF and H₂SO₄. The total sodium content fairly agreed with the sodium in borax and sodium chloride.

Determination of the Magnetic Susceptibility of the Samples.—The magnetic susceptibility of the samples was determined by Guoy's method in the Chemistry Department of the University College of Science, Calcutta. A constant current of 5 amp. checked by an ammeter and rheostat was passed. Blank experiments were done with the empty tube. The mass susceptibility χ_m was calculated from the following formula (Klemm "Magnetochemie")

$$\chi_m = 2.lz/mH_{max}^2.1.019$$

where χ_m is the susceptibility per unit mass of the substance (expressed in C.G.S. units per g.)

l is the length of the column of the substance in cm.

x is the change in weight in mg. and m is the weight of the substance in g.

H_{max} is the maximum strength of the magnetic field in Gauss. (In this case $H_{max} = 10.4 \times 10^3$ Gauss—determined against conductivity water as the reference substance. $\chi_s = -0.72 \times 10^{-6}$).

Care was taken to pack the substance as uniformly as possible by tapping, but this always left a source of error. The calculated values of the susceptibility of the alkali halides were determined from the additivity formula.

$$100\chi_s = p + \chi'_1 + (100 - p)\chi_2$$

where χ'_s is the observed mass susceptibility of the glass system,

χ_1 is the mass susceptibility of the dissolved alkali halide (to be calculated).

p is the percentage of the alkali in the glass, and

χ_2 is the mass susceptibility of the fused borax, it being assumed that the susceptibility of the borax in the glass remains unaltered. This last assumption has to be made (as is usually done) in all two-component systems, as for example in aqueous solutions. Otherwise the variation of both cannot be studied from a single equation. This method is used in calculating mole-refraction and specific refraction as well.

A second series of measurements was made by weighing out different quantities of fused borax and NaCl and fused borax and KCl, powdering each sample in an agate mortar without fusing and determining the magnetic susceptibility as before. Lithium chloride could not be tested in this manner because of its extreme hygroscopic nature. The susceptibilities of the pure substances were determined by Guoy's method in the same way and compared with the values given in the International Critical Tables and those determined by Bhatnagar and Mathur by the Int. balance.

TABLE I

MASS SUSCEPTIBILITY $\times 10^6$

Salt.	Guoy method.	International Critical Table.	Bhatnagar and Mathur.
LiCl	—	-0.572	—
NaCl	-0.4898	-0.499	-0.4902
KCl	-0.5208	-0.516	-0.5031
Borax glass	-0.4073	—	—

The susceptibility of salts determined by different workers vary presumably because of traces of paramagnetic impurities, uncertainty about dehydration and also because of the errors inherent in the different methods. The values in the first column are taken for our calculation; although not quite accurate, these will not seriously vitiate comparative results.

In the following tables, the observed mass susceptibilities of different samples of glasses are recorded in column 2; in column 3, the mass susceptibility of the dissolved halide calculated from additivity formula are given.

TABLE II

LiCl—BORAX GLASS

LiCl.	Mass susceptibility $\times 10^6$		
	Obs. for glass.	Calc. value for dissolved LiCl.	Value for LiCl (pure).
7.103%	-0.4248	-0.653	-0.572
8.365	-0.4295	-0.665	(Inter. Crit. Table)
11.490	-0.4408	-0.698	
13.05	-0.4562	-0.732	

TABLE III

NaCl—BORAX GLASS

NaCl.	Mass susceptibility $\times 10^6$		
	Obs. for glass.	Calc. value for dissolved NaCl.	Exp. value for NaCl (pure).
11.72%	-0.4289	-0.592	
12.25	-0.4513	-0.766	
16.27	-0.4613	-0.739	-0.4898
17.02	-0.4624	-0.731	
18.97	-0.4703	-0.739	
19.95	-0.4714	-0.728	

TABLE IV

KCl—BORAX GLASS

KCl.	Mass susceptibility $\times 10^6$		
	Obs. for glass.	Calc. value for dissolved KCl.	Exp. value for KCl (pure).
11.92%	-0.4373	-0.659	
13.31	-0.4439	-0.662	-0.5206
15.20	-0.4460	-0.662	
18.63	-0.4470	-0.620	

In the following tables, the mass susceptibility values of mechanical mixtures of NaCl-borax and KCl-borax are recorded. In column 2, the experimental value is given and in the last column, the value calculated from the additivity formula are recorded.

TABLE V

NaCl—BORAX GLASS MIXTURE

NaCl	Mass susceptibility $\times 10^6$	
	Obs.	Calc.
11.01%	-0.4259	-0.4163
12.50	-0.4273	-0.4175
14.00	-0.4296	-0.4183
16.00	-0.4306	-0.4206
18.02	-0.4379	-0.4222

TABLE VI

KCl—BORAX GLASS MIXTURE

KCl	Mass susceptibility $\times 10^6$	
	Obs.	Calc.
12.95%	-0.4182	-0.4219
13.31	-0.4191	-0.4233
14.53	-0.4246	-0.4235
16.00	-0.4275	-0.4255
18.11	-0.4349	-0.4279

DISCUSSION

Majumdar and co-workers have studied the change in mole-refraction and lattice distances of various alkali halides dissolved in boric oxide and borax glasses. The general conclusion arrived at by them are as follows : (i) Salts are more strongly deformed in glass systems than in corresponding aqueous solutions, and (ii) the deformation of the anion by the cation follows Fajans' deformation rule fairly accurately. Hence the deforming power of the cation on a common anion may be expressed by the inequality $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$.

Whether strict additivity relation exists in the case of solid diamagnetics has been studied among others by Gray (*Phil. Mag.*, 1930, *iv*, 10, 191; *Dakers, ibid.*, 1931, *iv*, 11, 81), Farquharson (*ibid.*, 1932, *iv*, 12, 283) and Kido (*Sci. Rep., Tokuhu Univ.*, 1932, 21, 149, 288, 869). Kido believes that the additivity relation exists in the case solid ionic crystals and drew up a table of ionic susceptibilities on this assumption. Hocart (*Compt. rend.*, 1929, 188, 1151) has made a careful measurement, taking particular care about the purity of the salt. The following table shows the values of molecular susceptibility of some salts studied by them.

TABLE VII
MOLECULAR SUSCEPTIBILITY

Salt	Kido	Hocart	Gray & Farquharson
NaCl	29.6	30.1	
KCl	35.8	39.1	39.1

The values obtained by us are 28.63 for NaCl and 38.82 for KCl. (for NaCl, $\chi_m \times 10^6 = 0.4998 \times 58.46 = 28.63$; for KCl, $\chi_m \times 10^6 = 0.5206 \times 74.56 = 38.82$)

The strict additivity rule which was assumed by these workers for ionic crystals cannot however hold good *absolutely*, because the outer electron density distribution of the ions in the crystals must be different from those of free ions. If χ_f , χ_c , χ_s represent respectively the values of magnetic susceptibility of the free ion, crystal and in solution respectively, then both χ_c and χ_s would be less than χ_f owing to the mutual interaction effects, which will bring about a change in electron density distribution, on which diamagnetism primarily depends. Brindley (*Phil. Mag.*, 1931, *iv*, 11 786) has discussed magnetic data from the standpoint of *effective ionic radii*, which are conditioned by the effective spread of electron density caused by surrounding ions or molecules. The diamagnetic susceptibility therefore gives a good indication of the space-charge distribution within the molecule.

Referring to our results, we find a smooth curve for susceptibility-concentration graphs for LiCl and KCl, whereas for NaCl the curve is not so smooth. One would naturally expect a smaller value of susceptibility for dissolved salts in the glass systems than in the pure crystalline state and this divergence should be maximum in the case of LiCl and decrease with the increase of the diameter of the cation (Fajans rule). Here we find however although the deviation of the value is most marked in the cases of all the three salts investigated by us, it is *in an opposite sense* to what would be expected from theory. For while the value of mass susceptibility of pure LiCl is -0.572×10^{-6} , the value calculated from the mixture

FIG. 1

Solid soln.

Curves I—III refers respectively to LiCl, NaCl and KCl

law varies between -0.653 and -0.782 ($\times 10^{-6}$) and this is also true, more or less, for the other salts. Another point to note in this connection is that in the case of LiCl, as well as in the case of NaCl and KCl, the value of the pure salt which would be obtained from extrapolation of the curves would have much higher negative values than the experimental values of the pure salts themselves. In the case of NaCl, the calculated value in the glass changes from -0.592 for a concentration of 11.72% to -0.728×10^{-6} corresponding to a concentration of 19.95% of the salt. The susceptibility-concentration curve unlike that of LiCl seems to be definitely bent. In the case of KCl, the calculated value of the susceptibility of the salt dissolved in the glass varies from -0.650 for a concentration of 11.92% to -0.620×10^{-6} , corresponding to a concentration of 18.63% of the salt.

Comparing the changes in susceptibility for unit change in concentration in the region of about 11.5—11.9% of the salt we get the following figures for the three salts :

LiCl, -1.09×10^{-3} ; NaCl, -8.7×10^{-3} and KCl, -1.16×10^{-2} .

In conformity with the mole-refraction data, one would expect the greatest change in the case of LiCl and least in the case of KCl. As has been stated before a decrease would be expected in every case, which is not an experimental fact. Moreover, KCl behaves also in anomalous manner. Whether this abnormal behaviour of this salt is due to inherent defects in the measurement or due to the presence of paramagnetic impurities has still to be decided.

Whether the glass systems studied by us represented simple solid solutions as in the case of alloys (simple) or homogeneous mixtures was further studied. LiCl had to be excluded from the investigation on account of its hygroscopic nature. As has been found

by Bhatnagar and Kapur (*loc. cit.*), the susceptibility-concentration curves are straight lines in the case of mixtures of salts which are not isomorphous and do not form solid solutions, whereas in these cases the curve passes through a maximum. The susceptibility-concentration curves of mixtures for NaCl and KCl are almost straight lines, the slight deviation

FIG. 2
Mixtures.

Curves I—II refer respectively to NaCl and KCl.

tions being due to experimental error. We can infer therefore that the systems previously studied are not simple mixtures following the additivity rule. In these cases however the explanation given by Bhatnagar and Kapur is inapplicable, as apart from the difference in formula type ($XCl-Na_2B_4O_7$) the molecular volumes are wide apart from that of the borax glass as would be seen from the following:

Substance	.. LiCl	NaCl	KCl	$Na_2B_4O_7$
Mol. vol. (c.c.)	.. 20.10	27.02	37.57	85.43

The conditions for isomorphous mixture are absent here.

Majumdar and Palit (*loc. cit.*) have shown that when polar crystals like NaCl are dissolved in a glass, the lattice structure of the former still persists; there is however a widening of the lattice distance. This has been further confirmed in the case of KCl (to be published in a separate communication). It is suggested by the authors that the increase in the lattice distance of the alkali halides is due to some sort of shielding action of the glass molecule on the electrostatic forces operating within the crystal. Roughly this means the Coulomb forces are weakened on account of the higher dielectric constant of the solvent medium. Whether the dielectric constant alone is sufficient to explain the change in lattice distance has still to be decided, but it is clear that this will also bring about a change in other physical properties like magnetic susceptibility, which is actually found to be the case.

The question in which state the dissolved salt exists in the glass has now to be discussed. Zachariassen, Warren and others believe that a *non-periodic* arrangement of the constituents obtains in the glass as opposed from a strictly periodic lattice arrangement of the same substance in the crystalline state. This is the reason why diffuse bands or haloes are obtained in X'ray diffraction photographs with glass instead of sharp lines as with crystals. It has been further established by Warren that in the case of borax and boric oxide glasses, the three valencies of the boron atom are arranged in a triangular manner and the linking is through oxygen atoms. In some cases the co-ordination number is found to increase. The cations of borax glasses like Na^+ , K^+ are supposed to lie in the empty spaces of this non-periodic network. In this case we might suppose that a regular periodic lattice of the alkali halide is formed within the glass, the alkali and the halogen ions taking up their positions in the empty spaces of the network in a three dimensional sense.

The forces operating between two neighbouring ions in a polar crystal are partly attractive (Coulomb forces) and partly repulsive (Born forces). Both of these forces will be affected by the surrounding atmosphere and the magnetic susceptibility of the crystal dissolved in a glass may be expected to be altered which is found to be the case experimentally. Further work on the subject is in progress.